

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Strategies for enhanced HPDA solutions designed
Milestone M3.2**

ESiWACE3 Milestone M3.2

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Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
BDA	Big Data Analytics
CLI	Command Line Interface
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CWL	Common Workflow Language
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ESM	Earth System Modelling
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FDB	Field DataBase
FDO	Fair Data Object
GRIB	GRIdded Binary or General Regularly-distributed Information in Binary form
HDF	Hierarchical Data Format
HPC	High Performance Computing
HPDA	High Performance Data Analytics
HTC	High Throughput Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MPI	Message Passing Interface
NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
WMS	Workflow Management Systems
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

This milestone report aims to describe a set of enhancements that will be explored in the context of the WP3 of the ESiWACE3 project to support High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA). Several types of strategies can be followed for enhancing data processing on large scale data. These can include the exploitation of novel storage solutions, e.g., not based on POSIX filesystem, for supporting improved access to climate and weather data, as well as solutions for improved reusability and reproducibility of the analysis.

The document serves as a base for guiding the implementation of the HPDA strategies. Its content will be updated in order to target additional requirements as the developments move on throughout the project. In particular, the final set of requirements, as well as the performed implementation and integration activities, will be described in deliverable D3.7 *“Report on exploiting the FDO for HPDA”*.

After providing an overview of the state of the art in the field of HPDA, including the key requirements, challenges and current solutions, the document describes a set of potential strategies that will be followed for improved HPDA on climate and weather data. A set of validation approaches for demonstrating the enhancements is also introduced. Finally, the document provides a summary and the plans for the HPDA enhancements within the project.

2. Background and challenges

In the last two decades, there has been an exponential increase in the data generated worldwide propelled by the advent of new instruments, technologies, faster supercomputers/networks as well as by the growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) and the widespread diffusion of mobile devices [1]. The term Big Data has emerged, at the beginning of the millenia, to describe these massive amounts of data, originally in terms of volume, velocity and variety [2].

The data growth had a significant impact on basically all industrial and scientific domains, including the weather and climate one. For example, in the climate domain the size of the data produced from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) has increased nearly 10 times from phase 5 (CMIP5) to phase 6 (CMIP6) of the project, to about 20PB [3]. Another notable example from the weather domain comes from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), which operates the largest meteorological data archive (called MARS) in the world storing, as of August 2023, around 450 petabytes of operational and research data, with about 300 terabytes of new data added daily [4]. Other very recent examples are the Digital Twins of the Earth developed within the Destination Earth initiative¹, which are expected to produce about 1 petabyte of data every day [5].

These Big Data represent a very valuable source of information for the study of climate and weather phenomena [6]. However, handling and processing such huge amounts of data carries several challenges in terms of data access, scalability of the analysis, reproducibility and results sharing [7].

¹ Destination Earth. Online: <https://destination-earth.eu>, last accessed on June 14, 2024.

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Big Data processing actually imposes strong requirements in terms of hardware and software infrastructure and needs High Throughput Computing (HTC) and High Performance Computing (HPC) solutions for efficient knowledge extraction. To this end, High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) solutions exploit the computational power of HPC jointly with advanced data processing capabilities for analysing large datasets efficiently.

It is worth noting that the High Performance Computing and Big Data Analytics (BDA) software ecosystems have been developed over different time frames and to address distinct requirements and workloads [8]. HPC workloads typically consist of tightly-coupled, massively parallel (MPI-based) batch applications, such as model simulations. Conversely, BDA workloads comprise heterogeneous, data-driven applications composed of loosely-coupled tasks and dynamic workflows, which evolved in the context of Cloud computing. Another key difference is related to the storage infrastructures, as HPC has been traditionally relying on parallel file systems and POSIX-compliant data access, while BDA has introduced novel distributed and cloud-based storage solutions.

Nevertheless, the two communities have been working in the last few years on the integration of the approaches and solutions from the two software ecosystems with the aim of creating a unified cyberinfrastructure that leverages the strengths of both, as also highlighted by some international initiatives like the Big Data and Extreme-scale Computing project (BDEC) [9]. Various efforts to port Big Data systems to HPC infrastructures are documented in literature [10-12]. However, their scalability is often limited due to ecosystem differences, requiring careful tuning and optimizations [13,14]. Thus, extended data analytics solutions able to integrate HPC technological advances, as well as climate/weather-specific data requirements have emerged to address HPDA effectively [15-18]. More recently, Python-based frameworks for climate/weather data have been developed by the community to support HPDA [19,20]. More details on the state of the art technologies are provided in the next section.

The rapid diffusion of Machine Learning (ML) algorithms in climate and weather domains has further propelled the need for efficient data management solutions able to handle large data volumes for data-driven models in the scope of HPC infrastructures (e.g., GPUs). Such integration plays a crucial role in supporting future scientific discovery [21].

Some of the key challenges when addressing HPDA applications are the following:

- *Efficient data access*: the increase in data volumes makes it of paramount importance to exploit novel techniques and storage solutions for improved data access. To this end, solutions like object storage or NoSQL databases represent alternative solutions to POSIX-based file systems for handling big data sources. In particular, object storage offers the advantage of fine-grained partitioning allowing access to specific subsets of a given dataset. Compression algorithms can also play a key role by substantially reducing the amount of data to be moved from the storage systems to the compute nodes;
- *Scalability of the analysis*: another important dimension to consider for efficient HPDA relates to the possibility of scaling the analysis on multiple compute units, also distributing it on different compute nodes. Parallel and distributed data processing exploiting common techniques from HPC, like multithreading and multiprocessing, can effectively speed up the analysis on larger data volumes. To this end, novel storage

solutions supporting efficient parallel data access can also enable a greater degree of scalability in the analysis;

- *Democratisation of data analytics*: as the HPC infrastructures grow in size and capacity, their effective usage becomes more difficult, especially for general users who are not skilled in the HPC environment (e.g., based on batch schedulers). In line with Open Science principles, high-level interfaces based on Python, abstracting from the complexity of the underlying infrastructure, can simplify user interactions for data analytics experiments. Python represents nowadays the “de facto” standard for data science and provides a wide range of well-known libraries for data analytics and machine learning. Jointly with the use of graphical interfaces such as Jupyter Notebooks, it can notably lower the entry barrier for using HPC capabilities in data science;
- *Reusability and reproducibility of the analysis*: along with the dataset volumes and the computing infrastructure capabilities, the complexity of data analytics and processing pipelines is increasing as well. This hinders the capacity of running the same analysis chain on different infrastructures, affecting both its portability and reusability. Workflow allows coding the data processing steps through an abstract definition and automates tasks execution to make the overall processing more repeatable, at least on the same infrastructure. Besides the workflow definition, reusability requires that also the input datasets can be univocally and automatically identified. FAIR data principles (i.e., Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) can help in this direction [22]. Thus, a stronger integration of HPDA workflows together with FAIR-compliant objects (e.g., input data, workflow definition, final results) can enable higher reusability of the analysis targeting reproducibility.

3. State of the art on data analytics solutions

HPDA applications can consist of single batch applications running workflows of multiple processing steps or as interactive and in-situ analysis.

- *Workflow Management Systems (WMS)* provide tools for researchers to define, execute, publish, and document their workflows consisting in the (parallel) execution of data acquisition, integration, cleaning, transfer, storing, analytics, result publication, and visualisation [23]. These systems can sometimes support the integration of simulation and analytics operations, enabling real-time data analysis and dynamical steering of the execution. Standard representations for defining workflows description, such as the Common Workflow Language (CWL) [24], have been designed to improve portability across platforms and reproducibility of experiments, though their use across workflow systems is not widespread yet;
- While HPDA workflows can be considered as batch applications executed as a single job or as a set of jobs on the computing infrastructure, *interactive analytics* refers to a computing approach where users and systems engage in a dynamic and responsive dialogue. This interaction is characterised by immediate feedback and adjustments based on user inputs;

- Other paradigms allow linking simulation and analysis in HPC, such as out-of-machine and *in-situ analytics*. The former involves running the simulation on one machine and the analysis on another, with the advantage of dedicated computing resources for each task. This approach usually requires storing large amounts of data in a parallel file system, which can create I/O bottlenecks. The latter performs simulation and analysis on the same machine, as soon as data is available in memory, eliminating intermediate storage needs. This method reduces I/O overhead and optimises resource usage, but requires careful management of shared resources. Real-time data analysis is an example of in-situ operation; other examples are data compression, indexing, and online visualisation. *In-transit processing* is another variant, where analysis is done on separate nodes dedicated to this purpose, despite the added data transfer costs.

This section provides an overview of the state of the art for data analytics solutions concerning workflows and interactive analytics, as these are more common and decoupled from a specific model implementation. In particular, the section will introduce (i) some solutions from the Python ecosystem, followed by (ii) the key data access technologies and (iii) a set of WMS.

a. Data analytics from the Python scientific software community

Multiple HPDA solutions are available within the Python ecosystem, either developed natively in Python or providing bindings. In this context, Dask [25] certainly represents one of the most interesting frameworks for HPDA: it offers a flexible solution for parallelizing Python computations across multiple nodes of a computing cluster, both HPC and Cloud-based. Dask decomposes the Python script to be executed as a direct acyclic graph of tasks, considering data dependencies, and implements its own schedulers for dynamic and parallel task execution. Dask integrates with popular Python data analysis tools like NumPy and Pandas and it supports execution on HPC clusters through plugins for common job schedulers (SLURM, LSF, etc.)

Several domain-specific projects are exploiting the Dask framework as the parallel compute engine to scale the analysis for bigger datasets. Some examples in the field of climate and weather include xarray [19] and Iris [26], which provide support for domain-specific operations and file formats. Both modules provide data cube-based abstractions to handle multidimensional data and integrate with other Python libraries for analysis and visualisation. For instance, xarray adopts a model similar to well-known scientific file formats, i.e., the Network Common Data Format (NetCDF) and Hierarchical Data Format (HDF). More details on xarray are provided in the next section.

Such packages are sometimes bundled together in software stacks, such as the scalable open-source analysis stack called Pandata [27] that covers data access, distributed computation, and interactive visualisation across various domains and scales. Pangeo is another example of a data analytics stack specifically tailored for geosciences [28].

b. Data formats in the climate and weather community

In the climate domain, the most used scientific formats are NetCDF and Zarr, while the GRIB (GRIBbed Binary or General Regularly-distributed Information in Binary form) format is also commonly used in the weather domain.

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NetCDF [29] provides a set of software libraries and machine-independent data formats that support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data. Its latest version, NetCDF4, relies on another well-known data format, i.e., HDF5 [30].

NetCDF is designed for high performance I/O and is widely used in climate science, meteorology, and oceanography. The advantages of this data format are:

- efficient handling of large array-based datasets;
- support for data compression and chunking (through HDF5), improving storage efficiency and access speed;
- extensive support for metadata, facilitating data sharing and interoperability. Specific metadata conventions like the CF-conventions have been established by the community for datasets created with the NetCDF API [31];

Zarr [32] is a more recent data format for the storage of chunked, compressed, N-dimensional arrays. It is particularly suited for cloud-based environments due to its design for parallel I/O operations. The advantages of this data format are:

- optimisation for parallel reading and writing, making it suitable for large-scale data analytics;
- support for various compression algorithms, allowing for flexible storage optimization;
- compatibility with various storage backends, including local file systems and cloud object stores like Amazon S3 and Google Cloud Storage.

NetCDF is robust for traditional scientific computing environments where interoperability and extensive metadata support are crucial. Zarr shines in cloud-based analytics due to its efficient parallel I/O operations and flexible storage backend compatibility. In line with the integration of the data-oriented and compute-oriented ecosystems, solutions based on object storage are being used more commonly for storing results from climate/weather numerical simulation produced by HPC centres. The developers of NetCDF library have therefore recently integrated specific plugins to handle Zarr datasets from the NetCDF API. By exploiting this feature, a number of BDA applications originally designed to process NetCDF datasets could effectively be used to process Zarr datasets simply by activating the NetCDF extensions, including the optimizations for parallel I/O operations, chunking, compression, etc.

GRIB [33] is a standard format from the World Meteorological Organization for archiving, handling and distributing gridded data and it is typically used for weather forecast data. The advantages of this format include:

- compactness: GRIB files are highly compressed, reducing storage requirements and enabling faster data transfer;
- efficiency: designed for large datasets, GRIB efficiently stores and accesses gridded data, which is common in weather models and forecasts;
- standardisation: GRIB is an international standard for meteorological data, ensuring consistency and interoperability across different systems and institutions;
- metadata richness: GRIB files contain comprehensive metadata, making it easier to understand and use the data without needing external documentation;
- flexibility: it supports a wide range of data types and grid structures, accommodating various scientific and operational needs.

In order to handle short-term storage and access to GRIB data from weather forecasting, ECMWF has developed a domain-specific object store called Field DataBase (FDB) [34]. FDB manages the final output stage for the I/O stack in ECMWF's Integrated Forecasting System (IFS). Specifically, it controls meteorological data output, defining data structures and usage patterns for storing data, and handles I/O processes and data writing while aggregating data from more compute nodes into local fields. Furthermore, FDB acts as a cache for accessing recently produced meteorological fields, which represent most of the forecast data required by external clients. FDB provides C++ API and command line interface (CLI) tools. The Polytope Python library², also from ECMWF, can be used as a higher-level interface for accessing and extracting data from datacubes, by selecting any arbitrary n -dimensional polygon (called a *polytope*), on top of FDB object stores or other backend systems (e.g., xarray data arrays) [35].

c. Workflow management systems for climate and weather

As previously mentioned, workflows represent an important strategy for HPDA. A workflow is not only the computing application, but it allows documenting the process. To this end, workflows can include metadata useful to track results provenance. Several solutions are available in literature to handle data processing workflows and each scientific domain seems to have its own preferred solution [23,36]. For the sake of simplicity, we will outline only some of the workflow management systems used by the climate and weather community.

Cylc [37] has been designed to manage complex and large-scale workflows (in scientific and research environments, meteorology, climate modelling). It specifically focuses on scheduling and dependency management, and provides robust features for workflow monitoring, visualisation, and error handling. It can schedule tasks based on time, external events, and dependencies on other tasks as well. Another tool used within the weather community is ecFlow [38], a workflow management tool developed by ECMWF to control complex suites of interdependent tasks, typically in operational and research environments. ecFlow allows users to define workflows by using a tree structure, where tasks are represented as nodes. It supports features such as job scheduling, error handling, and real-time monitoring, making it suitable for managing large-scale, time-critical workflows in fields like meteorology and climate science. Finally, Autosubmit [39] is a Python-based workflow manager developed by BSC, and supported also within the ESiWACE3 project, that is aimed at creating, managing and monitoring complex workflows involving multiple substeps. It can handle the orchestration of the tasks on multiple computing systems, from HPCs to post-processing clusters or workstations.

An interesting HPDA solution, supporting also complex workflows, is the Ophidia framework [40]. The framework implements a number of analytics operators by means of MPI and multithreading. Although it targets mainly the climate domain, it has been used in multiple scientific domains successfully [41]. Ophidia embeds a WMS tightly coupled with the underlying framework to efficiently handle workflows of Ophidia and non-Ophidia operators (e.g., CDO [42], NCO [43], bash scripts, etc.). It implements a client-server approach through a web frontend, enabling the user to submit single tasks or complex workflows over an HPC cluster by means of a number of interfaces supporting secure remote access, authentication and authorization. It also provides a Python client called PyOphidia. With respect to the

²"Polytope library". Online: <https://github.com/ecmwf/polytope>, last accessed on June 14, 2024.

previous solutions, it is oriented towards HPDA workflows rather than Earth system modelling (ESM) workflows. More details on this solution are provided in the next section.

Finally, by providing the complete description of a HPDA application, a workflow document can also address Open Science principles, and in particular the reusability of the analysis. Open Science is revolutionising the way research is conducted and shared, promoting greater transparency, accessibility, and collaboration across scientific communities. In order to meet Open Science goals, it is important to fully support the research process, which also includes addressing reproducibility of analytics workflows, a key requirement to promote data trustworthiness, reliability, accuracy, and integrity. Moreover, reproducibility implicitly fosters reusability, which is one of the FAIR guiding data principles [22]. By adhering to these principles, researchers can contribute to a more open and collaborative scientific ecosystem, thus accelerating discovery and innovation. It is worth noting that multiple conditions must be met to support full reproducibility of the analysis, e.g., providing a full description of the input data and the infrastructure used, besides the set of steps run for performing the analysis. Nevertheless, several efforts in literature have been made towards reproducibility targeting reusability and sharing of computational experiments [44-46].

4. Overview of key HPDA technologies

Following the challenges and advancements from literature, within Task 3.3 of the project we have been focusing on HPDA solutions providing support for scalable analysis with high-level APIs. Such solutions will form the analytical backend of a web-based programmatic platform based on Python. In particular, we are considering interfaces, such as Jupyter Notebooks, that enable users to perform interactive and parallel data analytics over HPC infrastructures. Besides providing the platform for testing the HPDA applications, notebooks also allow users to easily document and share their analysis and can represent a valuable tool for demonstrating the HPDA enhancements, for example in training events.

In terms of HPDA tools, we have been considering two modules providing Python interfaces that can easily be interfaced with Jupyter Notebooks to handle climate and weather datasets: *PyOphidia* and *xarray*. Both tools are used within the climate community, provide support for well-known formats like NetCDF and can perform parallel data analysis on different computing platforms. Among the key differences, *PyOphidia/Ophidia* provides direct integration of a WMS, while *xarray* is more flexible in terms of data formats supported and integration with other Python modules for data visualisation.

More in detail, *PyOphidia* is an open-source Python library designed for HPDA on multi-dimensional scientific datasets, particularly suited for climate and environmental data [20]. Developed by the CMCC as a frontend for *Ophidia* framework, *PyOphidia* provides a high-level abstraction for parallel data analysis, simplifying the execution of complex workflows on HPC infrastructures. *PyOphidia* addresses the needs of fast computing resources, advanced workflows, and parallel processing at scale, and it allows scientists to perform HPDA operations on scientific datacubes. This tool aims to bridge the gap between HPC and big data analytics, providing an interface that abstracts the underlying complexity of the infrastructure. An overview of its architecture is presented in Figure 1. The key features and capabilities can be summarised as follows:

- High-Level Abstraction: PyOphidia simplifies the execution of parallel data analysis by hiding the complexities of the underlying HPC infrastructure; this allows scientists to focus on their research without needing deep technical knowledge of HPC systems.
- Integration with Python ecosystem: the library integrates seamlessly with existing Python libraries and tools, making it easy to incorporate into various data science workflows; it supports integration with popular libraries such as NumPy and Pandas, facilitating a smooth transition for users familiar with these tools.
- Scalable data analysis: PyOphidia is designed to handle large-scale data analytics tasks efficiently; it leverages the capabilities of the Ophidia framework for managing and analysing large multi-dimensional arrays, making it suitable for applications that require processing vast amounts of climate and environmental data.
- Support for scientific datacubes: the library specifically targets the analysis of scientific datacubes, which are commonly used in climate research; this focus ensures that PyOphidia is well-suited to the unique needs of this domain.
- Parallel execution: PyOphidia enables parallel execution of data analysis tasks as well as complex workflows, improving performance and reducing processing times; this capability is crucial for handling the large datasets typical in scientific research.

Moreover, leveraging the development from ESiWACE2, the PyOphidia module has been recently extended with a workflow-oriented API that allows building analytics workflows and monitoring their execution. Support for workflow provenance will also be available in the future. PyOphidia has been effectively used in various scientific domains, particularly in climate and environmental research. Its ability to manage and analyse large-scale datasets makes it an useful tool for researchers who need to process and interpret data from complex simulations and observations.

Figure 1. Architecture of the PyOphidia module. The Python module interacts with the server side for the execution of the data analytics operators on the HPC/Cloud infrastructure (from [20])

Xarray is an open-source project and Python package that makes working with labelled multi-dimensional arrays simple and efficient, making it ideal for complex data analysis tasks in scientific research [19]. Built on top of NumPy and Pandas, xarray is tailored for use in

scientific data analysis, and in particular for the weather and climate domains. Its data model has taken inspiration from the NetCDF format³. The key advantages of xarray are:

- easier manipulation and analysis of multi-dimensional arrays with labelled dimensions and coordinates;
- seamless integration with Dask for parallel computation, enhancing performance on large datasets. Thanks to this integration, complex processing can be transparently distributed on multiple compute units and nodes;
- provision of wrappers for easy visualisation of datasets through matplotlib and cartopy libraries, which are well suited for geographical data;
- support of a wide range of data formats, including NetCDF, HDF5, Zarr, GRIB, GeoTIFF and other rasters providing flexibility in data read/write options.

Although not providing direct support for workflows, other Python solutions can be used to run xarray-based data analytics workflows.

5. Strategies for enhancing HPDA

Enhancements to HPDA can be achieved by following multiple strategies. Starting from the key challenges outlined in section 2, the following paths for enhancements have been identified:

- Path 1: use of novel data formats and storage solutions for improved data access;
- Path 2: looking towards reproducibility of data analytics applications through the use of FAIR-enhanced objects.

The selected tools (PyOphidia/Ophidia and xarray with Dask) already provide support for parallel processing and the enhancements should directly benefit from their scalability. In terms of ease-of-use, as both the solutions provide Python interfaces, Jupyter Notebooks running the analysis on top of the HPC infrastructure will be implemented as demonstrators and made available to end-users. For supporting the portability of HPDA on different HPC infrastructures, package management solutions like Conda environment⁴ or Spack⁵ are generally sufficient. Nevertheless, Docker containers bundling together the HPDA frameworks, the example notebooks and the Jupyter interface will be provided to support wider usage and evaluation of the enhanced HPDA solutions. The following subsections describe the selected HPDA enhancement strategies more in detail.

a. Path 1: use of novel data formats and storage solutions for improved data access

In this first strategy, the goal is to integrate data formats for HPDA by taking into account alternative formats to NetCDF for accessing climate datasets, starting from Zarr. As previously

³ "Xarray documentation". Online: <https://docs.xarray.dev/en/stable/user-guide/data-structures.html>, last accessed on June 14, 2024

⁴ "Conda documentation". Online: <https://conda.io/projects/conda/en/latest/user-guide/getting-started.html>, last accessed on June 14, 2024.

⁵ "Spack documentation". Online: <https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>, last accessed on June 14, 2024.

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mentioned, Zarr is a file format that has been gaining quite some traction in the climate community, and it allows accessing data from Cloud-based object storage solutions like S3. In this case, the focus is on extending the file formats supported by the Ophidia framework since the xarray library already supports the Zarr format. Integration with other storage solutions will also be evaluated later on in the project if there is an actual benefit for the users. Besides the integration, some experimental evaluation will also be carried out to understand the performance and scalability of the integrated format in the scope of common HPDA operations.

Initial work has already been performed during the first 18 months of the project for the integration of the Zarr format into Ophidia. The first part of the work focused on understanding how to enable the reading of Zarr files from the Ophidia back-end components, which are implemented in C. To this end, the best solution we found is to exploit the NetCDF API through the NCZarr plugin⁶. The main motivation for adopting such a solution is that this represents (at the time of writing this document) the only C-based API for accessing Zarr files. Nevertheless, as the Ophidia framework already integrates the NetCDF API for handling NetCDF v3 and v4 datasets, the approach proved to be quite effective since it allowed easy integration of the new format through rebuilding the libraries and making minimal changes to the code. Moreover, while testing the integration, a few issues were spotted and pointed out to the NetCDF developers, e.g., while accessing data from Pangeo on Google Cloud Platform and from the OpenStack Swift object storage. The fixes are publicly available on the main branch of the NetCDF code repository on GitHub⁷.

Figure 2 shows how the integration of the Zarr format in Ophidia is enabled through the C NetCDF API.

Initial integration tests have been carried out at CMCC, DKRZ and CSC clusters. Although both Ophidia and NetCDF, and all the related dependencies, are available through the Spack package manager, manual building of the code was required in order to enable the proper extensions. Once the integration has been further validated, the Spack setup procedure will be updated to enable the extensions automatically.

The evaluation of the Zarr support in Ophidia will be carried out following two approaches:

- performance evaluation concerning simple pipelines of data loading and processing; to this end, different types of operations (working on the temporal vs the spatial dimensions) will be planned in order to evaluate the execution time and the effect of file chunking from the Zarr format;
- running a workflow of multiple operations, for example the computation of a climate indicator, to validate the integration in terms of parallel and concurrent access to multiple Zarr files (or portions of files).

This HPDA enhancement can also benefit from the work done in task 3.1 about data layouts, and task 3.2 about data compression. The evaluation of such developments will also be taken into consideration as part of this activity.

⁶ "NetCDF documentation, NCZarr". Online: https://docs.unidata.ucar.edu/nug/current/nczarr_head.html, last accessed on June 14, 2024.

⁷ "NetCDF, pull request #2763". Online: <https://github.com/Unidata/netcdf-c/pull/2763>, last access on June 24, 2024.

Figure 2. Ophidia back-end software architecture highlighting the integration with the Zarr file format. Access to Zarr files is still performed through the NetCDF API using the proper NCZarr extension.

b. Path 2: looking towards reproducibility of data analytics applications through the use of FAIR-enhanced objects

The second strategy for enhanced HPDA focuses on data analytics applications, where several files might need to be accessed together to carry out the computation (e.g., HPDA workflows). In this case, supporting the reusability and reproducibility of the analysis can be quite challenging. The idea behind this strategy is to rely on FAIR objects to better support workflow reproducibility, in particular in terms of: (i) data access and (ii) publishing the results.

Concerning the first point, before running the analysis session on multiple data, scientists usually perform a search and selection process exploiting different solutions, e.g., manual selection from the file system, web-based interfaces and queryable data catalogues. In particular, we are interested in the use of data catalogues as a starting point for the selection of datasets. This first step is important and it can be considered as a prerequisite for identifying the actual location of the files that will be used for the analysis. However, this step is not usually part of the workflow.

The key point of this approach is to map the process of querying and selecting the input data from the catalogue(s) into additional steps of the workflow. As data catalogues are nowadays also registered with persistent identifiers (i.e., DOIs) and enriched with metadata (see [47] for an example from nextGEMS catalogue), this first step can exploit the identifier of the FAIR-compliant catalogue as an input to the workflow. Specific extensions will be developed for

this purpose. As different types of cataloguing conventions and systems exist, this experimental implementation will focus on some examples about some of the most used cataloguing tools used by the ESM community: intake⁸ and STAC⁹. Information about the cataloguing solution could potentially be attached to the catalogue metadata description, providing a more technical specification. The use of the FDO concept developed in task 3.3 of ESiWACE3 can be exploited to further generalise the FAIRness of the data objects and support data management and analytics-oriented metadata. Such activity is still a work in progress and the set of relevant metadata info to be included in FDOs is not clearly defined yet. Moreover, provenance associated with the results from the HPDA session could be enriched with additional information coming from the source FAIR catalogue.

The second point relates to enhanced FAIRness in results produced by data analysis or an HPDA workflow. Once the analytics session is completed, the scientists might need to share the resulting data with the wider community. Results, e.g., in NetCDF or Zarr, could already carry the required metadata, but these would need to be published on an open repository with a persistent identifier in order to be findable and accessible. This step is not typically part of the analysis and is carried out after its completion. Providing support for running such steps as an integral part of the analytics pipeline or workflow, assuming that the proper data quality controls are also ensured, could simplify sharing of the data results. Solutions like Zenodo [48], an Open repository for EU-funded research outputs, provide APIs that can be used for such purposes. A specific extension will be thus developed to map this process as a specific (optional) task of the analytics workflows.

Again the FDO concept developed in task 3.3 can be leveraged for the production of generalised FAIR data objects. In this context, provenance documents produced at the end of the HPDA workflow could become an integral part of the metadata associated with the results, thus providing better tracking of the steps that led to the generation of the results, and directly contributing to their reusability and reproducibility.

Figure 3 presents a general view of the workflow highlighting the steps related to the FAIR objects presented above. The workflow can start from a FAIR data catalogue accessible through a DOI or another persistent identifier from an open repository. Specific extensions based on community tools will be implemented to link the catalogue to the HPDA application steps run on the HPC infrastructure. The results, if the proper metadata is set to make them FAIR-compliant, could then be published on another open data repository. The full procedure could be either a Python application (e.g., a notebook) or a workflow document, and stored on an open platform (e.g., GitHub, WorkflowHub¹⁰). The direct integration of the two steps into an HPDA workflow is aimed at providing an automated way of increasing the FAIRness of the results and the overall reproducibility of HPDA workflows.

In order to validate the extensions, Jupyter Notebooks with example interactive data analytics pipelines and workflows will be implemented (based on either PyOphidia or xarray). The notebooks will also document and demonstrate the use of the extensions. Single notebooks showing different applications of the FAIR-enhanced objects extensions for HPDA will be created, as well as a notebook showing the integration of all the extensions into a single HPDA

⁸ "intake documentation". Online: <https://intake.readthedocs.io/en/latest/overview.html>, last accessed on June 14, 2024.

⁹ "STAC - SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs". Online: <https://stacspec.org/en>, last accessed on June 14, 2024.

¹⁰ "WorkflowHub". Online: <https://workflowhub.eu>, last accessed on June 14, 2024.

workflow, as shown in Figure 3. Extensions for supporting additional data formats presented in the previous section can also be used in this kind of workflow.

Figure 3. Example of a HPDA workflow exploiting FAIR-enhanced objects according to the 2 points presented in this section.

6. Summary and project plans

This report is aimed at providing the motivation and description of the HPDA enhancements envisioned in task 3.3 of the project. It lays out the ideas and design to be explored for supporting the enhancements. Moreover, it highlights some of the potential benefits from the interplay with the other activities carried out in WP3 of the ESiWACE3 project (e.g., FDO and data compression).

The document is mainly intended for the developers within WP3 to guide them through the implementation activities and synchronise on the ideas. Nevertheless, its background work and challenges address general HPDA in climate and weather and could potentially be used as reference also from outside the project.

In terms of plans, all the developed extensions will be described and documented in Python-based Jupyter Notebooks. The notebooks will be made available, together with the extended code, on existing public repositories (e.g., GitHub). Moreover, to simplify the use and evaluation of the extensions, Docker containers integrating the HPDA software, the notebooks, and the Jupyter service will be made available.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that the report presented just the first step of the development process. The set of challenges and related requirements will be updated throughout the project following the iterative development stage, and the final version of the design and developments will be described in deliverable D3.7.

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